

IRRADIANCE AND SIZING FOR OPTIMAL PERFORMANCE OF A PV SYSTEM

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Abstract: *The dearth of reliable and stable electricity in remote and underserved areas in Nigeria is a major socio-economic developments concern. Prospective electricity consumers rely on fossil fuel-driven generators which impact negatively on human health and the environment and has a huge high maintenance and running cost. This study explored the design and sizing factors for each of the system components to prevent over sizing and under sizing and to ensure adequate, reliable, and cost-effective PV system design. The system analysis was done using Hybrid Optimization of Multiple Energy Resources HOMER and MATLAB Simulink based on site specific solar parameters of irradiance, temperature. Optimization configuration results show that utilization of 12,570KWh electricity per annum solar PV system has ₦95.14/KWh cost of energy COE and zero emission. Also, it avoids release of 5,518Kg of carbon-dioxide CO₂ emission per year and cost reduction of ₦130/KWh when compared with conventional grid power. Therefore, PV system deployment provides reliable, stable, environmentally sustainable alternative energy for electricity consumers in the sub-Saharan African countries.*

1. INTRODUCTION

There are growing concerns about environmental degradation, continuous reduction of fossil fuel reserves and the rapid world's population growth (Wang and Azam,2023). These necessitated quest for alternative energy sources to mitigate the dependency on fossil fuels (Zhang,2024; Bai and Liu,2023). Solar energy (radiation from the sun)

is the most abundant form of renewable energy available in the world to mitigate the aforesaid challenges (Al Garni and Awasthi, 2017; Rashad et al.,2015). Solar photovoltaic PV system uses PV panel to generate electricity from sunlight power to solve socio-economic problems partly posed by insufficient electricity (Emmanuel et al.,2021). Nigeria's power grid generates and distributes an average of 4,000 MW of electricity

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daily, which is significantly less than its total installed generation capacity of 12,522 MW across 23 power plants (Remteng et al.,2021). The main objective of this study is to analyze the procedure for optimal design and sizing of solar PV systems and compare economics and performance with utility considering prevailing weather conditions (Khali et al., 2023).

Usah et al., 2020 study comparative techno-economic analysis of 48KWh/day PV power plant for two different installation sites with different climatic conditions. They concluded that initial investment cost and unit cost of energy could be minimized by appropriate sizing of the PV power system components. In the work of Shah et al., 2018, a systematic method of assessing the area-specific potential of solar PV for rural electrification in Pakistan was developed. They performed analyses that showed a well sized and design PV system according to standards has the potential to mitigate 126,000 metric tonnes of CO₂ emissions annually. Also, Szabo et al., 2011 examined cost-effective electrical technologies that might be deployed in rural regions of Africa. They carried a study to compared diesel generators, grid extension and PV technologies. The results showed that solar photovoltaic PV systems are economically feasible option and very competitive with diesel generators and extension of the transmission line in undeserved and large remote areas where the extension costs would increase the electricity price around 10-15 cents / kWh. Furthermore, Olatomiwa et al., 2014 designed and modelled

hybrid PV-wind-diesel system sizing for off-grid remote location mobile telecom base transceiver station in Nigeria considering the area-specific renewable energy resources potential using HOMER 2.81. The study was performed using rural site telecom base station hourly profile load demand, 37KWh average daily consumption and 3.3 KW peak demand considering the site-specific data for components modeling and simulation in HOMER for different system configurations. The results revealed that hybrid PV-wind-diesel system could reduce cost of power generation and decrease CO₂ emissions to 2,207 tonnes of CO₂ a year and concluded that it is the cheapest energy cost when compared to hybrid PV-diesel and diesel-battery systems. In the work of Jakub et al., 2020, they designed and analysed off-grid PV-battery system for remote power supply for four variable loads. They established that properly designed PV-battery systems can ensure reliability at a level comparable to conventional diesel generators. And concluded that reliability and performance of the PV-battery system is affected not only by temperature and irradiance fluctuations but also by a battery capacity and solar PV system efficiency reduction. Also, Guzman et al., 2020 carried out a study to determine sizing methodology for reduction of unused solar power in non-energy storage PV system considering the coupling of the potential solar energy and electric load through a dynamic simulation and financial evaluation. The simulation of combined photovoltaic energy

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potential and electric load characteristics with different PV power plants sizes without consideration for energy storage. The analysis results showed a reduction in the uncertainty of solar power and electric load coupling from 40% to 2.2%.

Despite all the previous studies of harnessing solar energy using PV technology to mitigate inadequate electricity access, global warming and carbon dioxide emission, there has been limited focus or studies on how to efficiently harvest solar energy in Effurun considering site-specific solar energy potential. This paper presents efficient and optimal approach to the

exploitation of solar energy resources in Effurun, Delta State, Nigeria to achieve Sustainable Development Goal 7 on affordable and clean energy. The key objectives are: proper sizing and system components selection to meet the user's energy demand with respect to geographical locations; analyze the designed and sized PV system in HOMER Pro; evaluate the effects of irradiance variation on the output of the sized solar PV system; analyze the techno-economic feasibility and viability of utilizing solar PV system in a selected location in Nigeria; examine the reliability of designed and sized PV system and compare with the national grid / utility.

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2. METHODOLOGY

Two major software tools (HOMER and MATLAB): hybrid optimization of multiple energy resources HOMER was implemented to analyze Technical and Economic performance analysis while MATLAB was used to assess impact of varying weather conditions of irradiance and temperature on PV system. Figure 1 depicts HOMER optimization algorithm block diagram: input data (site meteorologic,

Figure 1: HOMER optimization algorithm block diagram (including input data (site meteorologic, electrical load, technology type and project configuration) and HOMER simulation results. National Aeronautics and Space Administration NASA is a repository of meteorological data.

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S/N	Appliance	Rating (W)	Qty	Total Rating	Running Hours/Day	AEUD
1	Light (Bulb)	60	8	360	5	1920
2	Light (CFL)	15	8	120	6	480
3	Ceiling Fan	60	5	300	3	900
4	Air conditioner	745	2	1490	3	4470
5	Phone	7	4	28	4	84
6	Lump sum load	1000	1	850	1	1000
		Total Power	3,148W or 3.148 KW		Total AEUD	8852 WH or 8.852 KWH

Table 1: FUPRE ELECTRICAL LABORATORY LOAD ESTIMATION

Table 2: Solar radiation zones (global horizontal irradiation)

Zones	Annual average solar radiation (KWh/m ² /day)	Sunshine duration (h/day)	Annual average of solar energy intensity (KWh/m ² /year)	States
Zone I	5.7 – 6.5	6.0	2,186	Borno, Yobe, Jigawa, Kano, Kaduna, Bauchi, Gombe, Adamawa, Plateau and Kaduna.
Zone II	5.0 – 5.7	5.5	2,006	Sokoto, Zamfara, Kebbi, Niger, FCT (Abuja), Nasarawa, Taraba, Kwara, some sections of Plateau, Benue, and Kaduna
Zone III	< 5.0	5.0	1,822	Lagos, Oyo, Osun, Ekiti, Kogi, Benue, Rivers, Delta, Imo Anambra, Abia, Enugu, Edo, Ondo, Bayelsa, Akwa-Ibom Cross-Rivers, Ebonyi

The load estimation in Table 1 was taken at Federal University of Petroleum Resources FUPRE Effurun, Warri, Delta State, Nigeria

Electrical Engineering Department Laboratory. FUPRE is on 5.51° latitude and 5.75° longitude. Figure 2 as interpreted in Table 1 shows that

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Effurun, Delta State is in Zone III with annual solar irradiance of 1,822 KWh/m²/year and Peak Sun Hour of 5 (Abam et al, 2014). Solar Irradiance as shown in Figure 2 is a measure of sunlight intensity or energy per square meter (kWh/m²) while the solar insolation expressed in KWh/m²/day is the solar energy that reaches a PV surface at any given time (Bhatia, 2022) The latter is a good measure of site potential solar energy resources. High solar insolation will result in greater module current output while low solar insolation results in lower current output as shown in Equation 1.

daily solar insolation - peak solar radiation is 1 kW/m².

$$E_o(KWH) = P_p(KW) \times PSH (H) \tag{1}$$

Where:

E_o is maximum theoretical energy output (KWh) of solar PV system; P_p is peak power output (KW) of the array; PSH is the Peak Sun Hours (H) at the site or installation location.

Peak Sun Hours (PSH) is the average daily solar insolation in units of kWh/m² per day is sometimes referred to as "peak sun hours". The number of peak sun hours is numerically identical to the average

Figure 2 : Nigeria Solar Irradiance

2.1 SIZING OF STAND-ALONE PV SYSTEM

Equation 2 shows sizing methodology for standalone solar photovoltaic PV system (Abo-Khalil et al, 2023). The calculated power demand and energy requirement for electrical engineering laboratory are given in Table 1:

The maximum PV array for the project is calculated using Equation 2:

$$W_{PV} = \frac{E}{PSH \times \eta_{sys}} \quad (2)$$

W_{PV} is array total wattage (summation of all PV modules peak wattage), E is total daily user energy requirement in Wh, PSH is the average Peak Sun Hours for the site, and η_{sys} is the system efficient which is a function of Performance Ratio PR (Walker and Desai,2021). A PR of 70% (total loss of 30%) considering system inefficiencies and interconnection power losses is considered for this project.

System sizing parameters are:

User energy requirement per day

$$= 8852 \text{ Wh/day (Table 1)}$$

Elect. Eng'g Lab. Peak Sun Hours

$$= 4.5 \text{ hours (NASA,2024)}$$

Selected PV module peak power

$$= 350W_p$$

Selected System Voltage

$$= 48 \text{ volts}$$

System efficiency

$$= 70\%$$

The system inefficiencies and power losses are due to dirt, temperature, shading, interconnection wiring, and energy conversions.

The system aggregate losses (De-rating Factor) result in cumulative derating factor of 30% leading to system efficiency of 70% to ensure system reliability and energy balance (Bhatia,2022).

PV array required wattage is calculated thus using Equation 2:

$$W_{PV} = \frac{E}{PSH \times \eta_{sys}} \\ = \frac{8852}{4.5 \times 0.70} = 2811W$$

So, array total panels required N_T (350W_p modules) based on W_{PV} calculated above is:

$$N_T = \frac{W_{PV}}{Module(W_p)} \quad (3) \\ = \frac{2811}{350W_p} = 8 \text{ panels}$$

Therefore, 8 pieces of 350W_p mono-crystalline modules are required to meet 8.852KWh daily energy requirements. The next is the array series-parallel panels configuration known as Panel Configuration and Evaluation of selected panel configuration.

➤ Panel Configuration:

It refers to the array's parallel-series solar panel connection and arrangement.

The series-parallel connection of selected 8 numbers 350W_p mono-crystalline solar panel depends on:

(1) panel open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) as stated in the datasheet = 43.8V

(2) selected controller maximum peak power M_{pp} voltage range (4000W Victron SmartSolar controller MPPT 150/70) or the

maximum PV open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) = 150V

(3) The maximum PV V_{oc} middle voltage is then selected as the design voltage so that Mpp range is neither too low or exceeded charge controller voltage limit. So that it will operate efficiently.

A string (panels in series) is calculated thus:

- Design PV open circuit voltage = middle of the max. PV open circuit voltage = $150V/2 = 75V$

Number of series panels N_s , design open circuit voltage, and selected panel open circuit voltage are related by Equation 4.

$$N_s = \frac{\text{Design}(V_{oc})}{\text{Selected Panel}(V_{oc})} \quad (4)$$
$$= \frac{75V}{43.8V} = 1.7 \text{ panels}$$

Therefore, a string consists of 2 panels connected in series.

Number of strings required for parallel connection are given in Equation 5 (Dinesh and Shree, 2011).

$$N_p = \frac{N_T}{N_s} \quad (5)$$

Where, N_p is number of PV modules in parallel; N_s is number of PV modules series; N_T (array total panels / PV system). N_T is the product of N_p and N_s .

Array total panels required (N_T) = 8 panels; rated 350W_p each

Number of string panels $N_s = 2$ panels

Therefore, $N_p = 8 / 2 = 4$ parallel strings

Therefore, 2800W Solar PV System required 8 panels: a string of 2 panels in series and 4 strings in parallel for an efficient and reliable design.

Solar array configuration is evaluated to ascertain that the charge controller V_{oc} and I_{sc} (short circuit current) are not exceeded.

V_{oc} evaluation:

Number of panels in series $N_s = 2$; open circuit voltage = 43.8 V; lowest temperature in Effurun = 22°C, temperature correction factor = 1.02 (Table 3.3). Table 3 is adapted from NEC Table 690.7.

$$\text{Controller } V_{oc} = N_s \times \text{Module } V_{oc} \quad (6)$$

Where, Controller V_{oc} is open circuit voltage at lowest temperature = 150V; N_s is number of panels; Module V_{oc} is open circuit voltage of one panel at lowest temperature

$(2 \times 43.8 \times 1.02)V = 89.4V < 150V$. Thus, it is confirmed okay.

I_{sc} Evaluation:

$$I_{rated} = N_{PV\text{-parallel}} \times I_{sc} \times F_{safe} \quad (7)$$

Where, I_{rated} is PV array current (minimum controller input current); $N_{PV\text{-parallel}}$ is total parallel strings; I_{sc} is panel short circuit current; F_{safe} is the safety factor.

Given: Number of parallel strings = 4; Panel short circuit current $I_{sc} = 10.43A$; Safety factor = 1.5

$$I_{rated} = 4 \times 10.43 A \times 1.5 = 62.58A < 70A$$

Results of Equations 6 and 7 show that panel configuration (2 string panels and 4 parallel strings) is proper and satisfactory for the selected MPPT Victron charge controller.

Table 3: Ambient Temperature Correction Factor

Ambient Temperature (°C)	Factor	Ambient Temperature (°F)
24 to 20	1.02	76 to 68
19 to 15	1.04	67 to 59
14 to 10	1.06	58 to 50
9 to 5	1.08	49 to 41
4 to 0	1.10	40 to 32
-1 to -5	1.12	31 to 23
-6 to -10	1.14	22 to 14
-11 to 15	1.16	13 to 5
-16 to -20	1.18	4 to -4
-21 to -25	1.20	-5 to -13
-26 to -30	1.21	-14 to -22
-31 to -35	1.23	-23 to -31
-36 to -40	1.25	-32 to -40

Voltage correction factors for crystalline and multifocal silicon modules at ambient temperatures below 25 °C (77 °F) are found in Table 3, which was taken from NEC Table 690.7.

Inverter Sizing

The inverter, assuming all the appliances are running simultaneously, is sized to meet 100% load requirements (Equation 8).

$$I_{size} = \frac{P_{load}}{I_{eff} \times PF} \times 1.25 VA$$

(8)

Where, I_{size} is the inverter power requirement or the nominal capacity; P_{load} is the user load requirement; I_{eff} is the inverter efficiency; PF is the inverter power factor considering system inductive load; 1.25 accounts for 25% safety

design margin (surge power requirements and future growth).

Load power requirement = 3148 W, Inverter Efficiency = 0.90, Power factor = 0.90 (due to present of inductive load). By applying Equation 3.8 to size inverter:

$$I_{size} = \frac{P_{load}}{I_{eff} \times PF} \times 1.25 VA$$

$$I_{size} = \frac{3148}{0.9 \times 0.9} \times 1.25 VA$$

$$I_{size} = 4858 VA \text{ or } 4.858 KVA$$

- The inverter capacity of 5KVA, 48V input voltage and 230V output voltage is appropriate. So Victron 48V/5KVA/230V single phase inverter is chosen for the design.

Battery Sizing

The fundamentals considerations in sizing battery or battery bank capacity for PV system

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are based on system operating voltage, depth of discharge, autonomy days (Dinesh and Shree, 2011).

$$C_B = \frac{E \times N_A}{\eta_B \times DOD \times V_{DC}} \quad (9)$$

C_B is required battery bank capacity, E is the daily energy requirement or daily energy consumption, N_A is the autonomy days, η_B is the battery charging efficiency, DOD is the depth of discharge, and the battery bus voltage or system design voltage V_{DC} .

(E) = 8852 WH, (N_A) = 5 days, (η_B) = 0.85, (DOD) = 0.8, V_{DC} = 48V. Selected battery is Exide 6E95-11 (Deep cycle battery) of 12V / 478 Amp-hour (Ah) capacity.

Therefore,

$$C_B = \frac{8852 \times 5}{0.85 \times 0.80 \times 48} \text{ Ah} = 1356 \text{ Ah}$$

Required Battery capacity C_B = 1356 Ah

Required batteries for parallel connection is given in Equation 3.10

$$N_{BP} = \frac{C_B}{C} \quad (10)$$

$$N_{BP} = \frac{1356}{478} = 2.84$$

Thus, 3 battery strings in parallel are needed.

N_{BP} is batteries in parallel; C_B is the calculated battery capacity; C is the selected battery in ampere-hours.

The numbers of batteries required in a string is given in Equation 3.11

$$N_{BS} = \frac{V_{DC}}{V_B} \quad (11)$$

$$= \frac{48}{12} = 4$$

Thus, 4 batteries in series are required (one string).

Where: N_{BS} is batteries in series; V_{DC} is the System voltage or DC voltage; V_B is rated voltage of the selected battery.

Therefore, total batteries required for efficient and reliable energy storage for the solar PV system is equal to the product of N_{BS} and N_{BP} as defined by Equation 12.

$$N_{BT} = N_{BP} \times N_{BS} \quad (12)$$

$$= 3 \times 4 = 12$$

Total batteries required for energy storage N_{BT} = 12 batteries: each rated 478AH.

Where: N_{BT} is total batteries in storage bank; N_{BP} is total parallel batteries; N_{BS} is total series batteries.

Three parallel connected strings of lead acid batteries make up the project's battery storage configuration. And Four 12V 478AH Exide 6E95-11 batteries make up each string.

Charge Controller Sizing

Among the widely used controller types (PWM and MPPT), Maximum Power Point Tracking MPPT charge controller manages energy more effectively than Pulse width Modulation PWM because it draws maximum available power from PV panel irrespective of variations in current-voltage characteristics.

MPPT charge controller is adequately sized for I_{rated} or controller minimum input current and I_{DC} or maximum DC load output current called rated battery charging current.

I_{rated} is as given in Equation 13:

$$I_{rated} = I_{SC} \times N_P \times F_{SAFE} \quad (13)$$

$$= (10.43 \times 4) \times 1.5 A = 62.58A$$

I_{rated} is the solar charge controller minimum input current; I_{sc} is PV module short circuit current; The safety factor, or F_{safe} , makes sure the controller can manage the highest current the array can generate. I_{sc} (HF-350W) = 10.43 A, $N_{parallel} = 4$, Safety Factor $F_{SAFE} = 1.5$

I_{DC} or controller rated is as stated in Equation 14

$$I_{DC} = \frac{P_{LOAD}}{V_{DC}} \quad (14)$$

I_{DC} is maximum DC input current; P_{LOAD} is load demand or requirement; V_{DC} is the system DC voltage or bus voltage.

Given: $P_{LOAD} = 3148 W$, $V_{DC} = 48V$

$$= \frac{3148}{48} = 65.58 A$$

Victron SmartSolar Charge Controller with rated charging current of 85A was selected.

Cable Sizing

Cable sizing and selection is vital for both solar PV system reliability and performance. Cable Sizing is based on the National Electrical Code and the Institution of Engineering and Technology's (IET) standards.

Copper has excellent conductivity which makes it suitable for project cable material. The size or cross-sectional area of copper wire or cable size according to (QT10,2013) Equation 15:

$$S = \frac{p \times L \times I \times 2}{V_D} \quad (15)$$

Where: S is conductor size (mm^2), p is resistivity of wire (copper $p = 1.724 \times 10^{-8} \Omega\text{-m}$], L is the conductor length, I is ampacity or maximum current carrying capacity, V_d is maximum voltage drop (3% for a single-phase system and 5% for a 3-phase system).

S/N	Component cable description	Sizing parameters	DC Cable size
1	PV array and charge controller input	L=8M; I=40; $V_d = 1.44$	10MM ² UV/XLPE
2	Charge controller output and Battery.	L=10M; I=66; $V_d = 1.44$	16MM ² PVC
3	Battery bank and 5KVA inverter input	L=8M; I=104.16 $V_d=1.44$	DC 20MM ² PVC

Table 4: DC Cable Sizing

2.2 BUILDING OF PV MODEL IN MATLAB/SIMULINK:

Figure 3 shows a practical solar PV cell equivalent circuit considering internal series

resistance R_s to current flow and a parallel current leakage resistor. Constant current source (photogenerated current) and diode are connected in anti-parallel.

Figure 3: Single-diode equivalent circuit of Practical PV device

Output current I_{pv} is proportional to irradiation and photogenerated current I_{ph} . By applying Kirchhoff law, output current I_{pv} or Photovoltaic current for practical single cell model is in Equation 16 (Edouard and Njomo, 2013).

$$I_{PV} = I_{PH} - I_D - I_P \quad (16)$$

The PV model in Figure 4 was developed using the MATLAB inbuilt PV characteristics equations. Figure 4 shows the complete PV model using elements / block function in MATLAB/Simulink library equivalent to solar PV electrical circuit devices. The practical PV mathematical model equations are given in Equations 16 to 20 (DeSoto et al., 2006, Driesse et al., 2007, Hussein et al., 1995 and Crispim et al., 2007).

$$I_{PV} = I_L - I_S * \left(\exp \left[\frac{q*(V_{PV} + I_{PV}*R_S)}{n*K*N_S*T} \right] - 1 \right) - \frac{(V_{PV} + I_{PV}*R_S)}{R_{SH}} \quad (17)$$

The voltage-current characteristic for solar cells as shown in Equation 17

$$I_S = I_{RS} * \left[\left(\frac{T}{T_0} \right)^3 * \exp \left[\frac{q*E_G \left(\frac{1}{T_0} - \frac{1}{T} \right)}{n*K} \right] \right] \quad (18)$$

The cell saturation current I_s varies with the cell temperature as shown in Equation 18

$$I_{RS} = \frac{I_{SC}}{\exp \left(\frac{q*V_{OC}}{n*N_S*K*T} \right) - 1} \quad (19)$$

The cell reverse saturation current is a function of cell short current I_{sc} , and open circuit voltage, is given in Equation 19:

$$I_{SH} = \left(\frac{V_{PV} + I_{PV}*R_S}{R_{SH}} \right) \quad (20)$$

The shunt current is a function of output voltage, internal voltage drop and parallel resistance is given in Equation 20.

$$I_L = I_{SC} + K_i * (T - 298) * \frac{G}{1000} \quad (21)$$

PV cell photogenerated current I_{ph} depends on solar irradiance and ambient temperature as shown in Equation 21.

Where $I_L = I_{ph}$ is the light or photogenerated current; I_d is diode current; $I_{sh} = I_p$ is parallel or shunt resistance current (A); I_s represents the diode's saturation current; R_s is series resistance; $R_{sh} = R_p$ is the parallel or shunt resistance; q is the electron charge ($1.6 \times 10^{-19}C$);

k = Boltzmann's constant ($1.38 \times 10^{-23}J/K$); $n = A$ is the ideality factor (1-2); T is cell ambient temperature in Kelvin (K); N_s is solar cells in series; I_{pv} is the module output current; V_{pv} is the module output voltage; G is solar irradiance; G_0 is reference solar irradiance; I_{LO} is reference photo-generated current; T_0 is reference temperature in Kelvin (K); K_i is the cell's short circuit current temperature coefficient ($0,0017A / \text{degree C}$); C_T is light generated current temperature coefficient.

Figure 4: Solar PV system single-diode model

The model is configured with required technical data from Manufacturer datasheet of

The model is configured with required technical data from Manufacturer datasheet of Sunenergy HF-350W monocrystalline solar PV cell and implemented in MATLAB / Simulink software to assess PV module I-V and P-V characteristics under two varying weather conditions of irradiance and temperature.

MATLAB/SIMULINK at two conditions:

(1) Varying irradiance from $200w/m^2$ to $1000w/m^2$ at interval of $200w/m^2$ at STC temperature (25 degree C)

(2) Varying temperature from 20 degree C to 40 degree C at interval of 5-degree C at STC irradiance ($1000 w / m^2$).

3.RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Analysis of the Photovoltaic System

HOMER simulation results shown in Figures 5 to 9 and Table 8 validate the aim and objectives of this study.

Figure 5 shows geographical details of Effurun with data acquired from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration data base NASA. It is obvious that clearness values are nearly the same throughout the whole year

radiation is very diverse. Average daily solar radiation value or insolation in Effurun is at maximum in months of January and February (5.330 KWh/m²/day) and at a minimum in July (3.330 KWh/m²/day).

(0.565 in January and 0.332 in July) while solar

Figure 5: The average monthly radiation data and clearness values in Effurun

Figure 6a shows the variation of Effurun ambient temperature over the year. Average ambient temperature of 25.59-degree centigrade is almost the same as STC temperature. Also, Figure 6b depicts the monthly average - wind speed over the year wind with an annual average - wind speed of 3.08m/s measured at 50m above the earth surface (anemometer height). The analysis means wind - energy is not feasible in Effurun compared with Northern region of Nigeria with an average wind - velocity of at least 6m/s (Sokoto, Kano, Borno, Plateau etc).

Figure 6a: The monthly average temperature data

Figure 6b: The monthly average wind speed

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Figure 7: Seasonal electrical load profile

Figure 7 shows seasonal electrical load profile with peak demand of 1.64KW and 8.85 kWh/day daily energy demand. Also, it depicts HOMER result for solar PV system for every hour at 60 minutes time step with load demand is high in July - 2.0 KW and November–2.09 KW and low in June –1.63KW and February – 1.69KW.

Figure 8 depicts the HOMER Pro generated the system model prior to simulation. The model is based on data defined in HOMER optimization algorithm flowchart. The data comprise site meteorological data obtained from NASA, electrical load, technology type and project configuration. Figure 8 illustrates how solar PV system components are interconnected and designed to functionally meet daily load demand independent of the grid power. HOMER then simulates the system operation and calculates the results based on the input data accordingly. The schematic shows 8.85 kwh/day daily energy demand, an average peak load of 1.64KW and rating of major system components (Solar Array, Battery Bank, Inverter, and Controller).

Figure 8: Electrical Laboratory Solar PV User System Model

Table 5 shows optimization results ranked in an increasing order of the net present cost NPC from top to bottom. It means that the lowest NPC is at top of the list. The life-cycle cost of an autonomous PV system (which includes the original capital cost, component replacement, operating costs and maintenance costs) is represented by HOMER NPC. Additionally, HOMER represents average cost of producing one KWh of energy by cost of energy COE. Table 4.2 depicts that cost of energy COE is N95.14 / KWh, whereas original capital cost and least net present cost NPC are ₦2,880,000, ₦3,970,000 respectively.

Table 5: HOMER optimization configuration results

Architecture					Cost				System		Solar Array		Battery Bank	
Solar Array (kW)	Battery Bank	Converter (kW)	Dispatch	COE (₦)	NPC (₦)	Operating cost (₦/yr)	Initial capital (₦)	Ren. Frac. (%)	Total Fuel (L/yr)	Capital Cost (₦)	Production (kWh/yr)	Autonomy (hr)	Annual Throughput (kWh/yr)	
9.44	3	1.47	LF	₦95.14	₦3,970M	₦84,712	₦2,880M	100	0	943,776	12,570	35.7	1,690	
9.44	3	1.47	CC	₦95.14	₦3,970M	₦84,712	₦2,880M	100	0	943,776	12,570	35.7	1,690	
9.58	3	1.45	LF	₦95.17	₦3,970M	₦84,381	₦2,880M	100	0	958,215	12,762	35.7	1,688	
9.58	3	1.45	CC	₦95.17	₦3,970M	₦84,381	₦2,880M	100	0	958,215	12,762	35.7	1,688	
9.47	3	1.47	LF	₦95.26	₦3,980M	₦84,736	₦2,880M	100	0	947,222	12,615	35.7	1,690	
9.47	3	1.47	CC	₦95.26	₦3,980M	₦84,736	₦2,880M	100	0	947,222	12,615	35.7	1,690	

The NPC is the summation of Capital, Replacement, and operational and maintenance costs of solar PV system.

Figure 9: Figure 1: I-V Characteristics @ varying input irradiance

Table 6: The NPC (capital, replacement, and operation and maintenance cost) for solar PV per component

S/N	Component	Cost (NGN)
1	Battery Bank	2,040,812.78
2	Solar PV array	944,955.76
3	System Converter	987,895.82
	TOTAL (NPC)	3,973,704.36

Table 6 shows that Battery (energy storage system) has the highest cost which is over two million naira (2,000,000 NGN). It means cost of battery units is higher than the other components sum together. The lower the cost of required battery energy storage, the lower the NPC. There are ongoing research and advancement in battery storage technology. The improvement in battery storage technology will reduce NPC in the nearest future and subsequently lower the solar PV COE.

3.2 Economics Analysis

Table 4.2 shows that solar PV cost of energy COE is ₦95.14k (₦95.14k/KWh). Grid power Band A tariff with

similar service is ₦225 / KWh by the mandate given by NERC to BEDC ([BEDC-MYTO-ORDER-JUNE 2024.pdf](#)).

Comparison of two power sources means a user saves an average ₦130 per energy unit (₦130 /KWh)

by implementation of an adequately designed solar PV system. Also, the stimulated solar PV system grants 24

hours of continuous supply whereas utility grants 20 hours of supply. Though, initial investment / capital

cost of two million, eight hundred- and eighty-thousand-naira NGN (₦2.88M) and net present cost NPC or

lifecycle cost of ownership of three million, nine hundred- and seventy-thousand NGN ((₦3.97M) for 8.85KWh

daily energy PV system might be too huge for an average Nigerian.

3.3 Optimal PV system performance

Solar PV system model in Figure 3 was simulated in MATLAB to demonstrate non-linear characteristics of PV module – to predict the behaviour of PV module under varying weather conditions. The simulation results in Figure 9

show relationship between output current I and output voltage V (I-V characteristics) under varying input irradiance.

The open-circuit voltage and short-circuit current increased with increasing solar irradiance from 200w/m² to 1000w/m² at interval of 200w/m² at STC temperature (25 degree C). The increment is a linear function of the solar irradiance, current increased more significantly than voltage.

Output power P and output voltage V relationship (P-V Characteristics curve) of HF-350 Module at varying input irradiance from 200w/m² to 1000w/m² at interval of 200w/m² at STC temperature (25 degree C) is as shown in Figure 10. The output power of a photovoltaic module is highly dependent on the solar radiation intensity that strikes its surface. The output power increases with increasing solar radiation intensity.

Figure 11 shows relationship between output current I and output voltage V of HF-350 Module (I-V Characteristics curve) at varying input cell temperature from 20 degree C to 40 degree C at interval of 5-degree C at constant STC irradiance of 1000 w /m². With increasing module temperature (20°C to 40°C), output voltage decreases substantially while output current increases marginally.

Figure 10:P-V Characteristics @ varying input irradiance

Figure 11: I – V Characteristics @varying input temperature

The output power of a photovoltaic module is highly dependent on the solar radiation intensity that strikes its surface as shown in Figure 12. The output power decreases with increasing the temperature.

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Figure 12: P-V Characteristics @ varying input temperature

4. CONCLUSION

The analysis of optimal PV system to meet an electrical load of 3.148KW with daily energy demand of 8.854KWh in Effurun, Delta State, Nigeria on latitude 5.33 degree and 4.5 KWh/m²/day insolation was implemented using HOMER Pro and MATLAB. The system is made of 8 panels, each rated 350W_p, divided into 2 rows each containing 4 panels. The analysis results showed 12,570KWh annual PV energy production and ₦95.14/KWh COE with NPC or lifecycle cost of ownership of three million, nine hundred- and seventy-thousand NGN (₦3.97M). Based on Nigeria GEF, 12,570KWh power grid energy generates equivalent of 5,518Kg CO₂ per year. The solar PV COE is lower

than The Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission NERC's ₦225/KWh for Tariff band A with near related hour of service. This study achieved a cost saving of about ₦130 per energy unit and mitigated 5,518Kg of CO₂ emission per year. The study shows that site-specific primary input data (Irradiance, temperature, clearness index, wind) and secondary input data (summation of capital cost, replacement, and operation and maintenance cost) are crucial for HOMER modeling and simulation. This project evaluated and compared the economic, reliability, merits, and demerits of both the conventional utility supply and the solar PV system. The study revealed that the optimal position and direction for Solar PV panel

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placement is South direction at 20 degrees (location latitude plus 15 degrees) tilt angle for fixed tracking solar PV to provide optimal energy production all year long. Though solar PV requires high initial investment, its economic viability due to low COE and environmental sustainability outweighs grid supply that has higher unit cost of energy with attendant high pollutants.

REFERENCES:

Abam, F., Nduka, N., Ohunakin, O., & Ojomu, S. (2014). Energy resource structure and on-going sustainable development policy in Nigeria. *International Journal of Energy and Environmental Engineering*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40095-014-0102-8>

Abo-Khalil, A. G., El-Sharkawy, I. A., Sayed, K., & Radwan, A. (2023). Analysis of the PV system sizing and economic feasibility study in a grid-connected PV system. *Case Studies in Thermal Engineering*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.csite.2023.102903>

Al Garni, H., & Awasthi, A. (2017). Techno-economic feasibility analysis of a solar PV grid-connected system with different tracking using HOMER software. In 2017 IEEE International Conference on Smart Energy Grid Engineering (SEGE) (pp. 217–222). IEEE.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/SEGE.2017.8052802>

BEDC. (2024, June). BEDC MYTO Order June 2024. Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission.

<https://nerc.gov.ng/wpcontent/uploads/2024/06/BEDC-MYTO-ORDER-JUNE-2024.pdf>

Bhatia, A. (2022). Design and sizing of solar photovoltaic systems. Continuing Education and Development, Inc. <https://www.cedengineering.com/userfiles/R08-002%20>

Crispim, J., Carreira, M., & Castro, R. (2007). Validation of photovoltaic electrical models against manufacturers' data and experimental results. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Power Engineering, Energy and Electrical Drives (POWER ENG)* (pp. 556–561).

DeSoto, W., Klein, S. A., & Beckman, W. A. (2006). Improvement and validation of a model for photovoltaic array performance. *Solar Energy*, 80(1), 78–88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2005.06.010>

Dinesh, K. S., & Shree, R. S. (2011). Training manual for engineers on solar PV system.

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<http://www.researchgate.net/publication/268387350>

Driesse, A., Harrison, S., & Jain, P. (2007). Evaluating the effectiveness of maximum power point tracking methods in photovoltaic power systems using array performance models. In Proceedings of the IEEE Power Electronics Specialists Conference (PESC) (pp. 145–151). <https://doi.org/10.1109/PESC.2007.4341982>

Edouard, M., & Njomo, D. (2013). Mathematical modeling and digital simulation of PV solar panel using MATLAB software. International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering, 3(9), 24–32.

Emmanuel, P., Agbo, C. O., Edet, T. O., Magu, A. O., Njok, C. M., & Ekpo, H. L. (2021). Solar energy: A panacea for the electricity generation crisis in Nigeria. Heliyon, 7(e07016). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e07016>

Guzman, J. J. M., Braga, S. L., Torres, J. C. Z., & Beltran, H. J. (2020). Sizing methodology for photovoltaic systems considering coupling of solar energy potential and the electric load: Dynamic simulation and financial assessment. Sustainable Energy

Technologies and Assessments, 42, 100862.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2020.100862>

Hussein, K. H., Muta, I., Hoshino, T., & Osakada, M. (1995). Maximum photovoltaic power tracking: An algorithm for rapidly changing atmospheric conditions. IEE Proceedings - Generation, Transmission and Distribution, 142(1), 59–64. <https://doi.org/10.1049/ip-gtd:19951525>

Jakub, J., Ceran, B., & Orłowska, A. (2020). Techno-economic evaluation of solar PV system for energy transition. Energy, 202, 118686. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.118686>

Olatomiwa, L., Mekhilef, S., & Huda, A. S. N. (2014). Optimal sizing of hybrid energy system for a remote telecom tower: A case study in Nigeria. International Journal of Photoenergy, 2014, Article ID 124081. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2014/124081>

QT10. (2013). QT10 data sheet. ABB. <https://library.e.abb.com/public/9b867d77d5e0da7fc1257ca60057221b/QT10%20EN%202013.pdf>

Remteng, C., Suleiman, M. B., Asoegwu, C. M., & Emenyonu, C. N. (2021). Nigeria

electricity sector overview. Energypedia.
https://energypedia.info/wiki/Nigeria_Electricity_Sector

climatic conditions. *Journal of Energy Systems*, 4(2), 45–54.

Sera, D., Teodorescu, R., & Rodriguez, P. (2007). PV panel model based on datasheet values. In 2007 IEEE International Symposium on Industrial Electronics (ISIE) (pp. 2392–2396). IEEE.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/ISIE.2007.4374981>

Walker, A., & Desai, J. (2021). Understanding solar photovoltaic system performance: An assessment of 75 federal photovoltaic systems. U.S. Department of Energy.
<https://www.energy.gov/sites/default/files/2022-02/understanding-solar-photovoltaic-system-performance.pdf>

Shah, S. A., Valasi, G. D., Memon, A. A., Laghari, A. N., Jalbani, N. B., & Strait, J. L. (2018). Techno-economic analysis of solar PV electricity supply to rural areas of Balochistan, Pakistan. *Energy Reports*, 4, 418–426.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2018.06.008>

Szabo, S., Bódis, K., Huld, T., & Moner-Girona, M. (2011). Energy solutions in rural Africa: Mapping electrification costs of distributed solar and diesel generation versus grid extension. *Environmental Research Letters*, 6(3), 034002.
<https://stacks.iop.org/ERL/6/034002>

Usah, E. O., Ozuomba, S., Enobong, J. O., & Etinamabasiyaka, E. E. (2020). PVsyst software-based comparative techno-economic analysis of PV power plant for two installation sites with different

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